

The layers of the Software Architecture

1. On-chain Storage Layer

Refers to the information and operations stored and performed on the Ethereum blockchain. Initially, we implemented a smart contract using the Solidity language, which stores references from each patient's records to associate them with ownership of such documents. In addition, the smart contract allows the storage of the concerns of each participant in the network that may have access to a patient's record. The pseudo-algorithm referring to the implemented RecordControl smart contract, will be detailed below.

Algorithm 1 RecordControl smart contract

```
1 Function includeOwner(recordID, pacientID, fileHash):
2   | Checks if msg.sender is different from administrador
3   | ownerVector[pacientID][recordID] = true
4   | include fileHash in fileHashVector[recordID]
5 End Function
6 Function includeAccess(recordID,heID):
7   | Checks if msg.sender is different from administrador
8   | accessVector[recordID][heID] = true
9 End Function
10 Function removeAccess(recordID, heID):
11 | Checks if msg.sender is different from administrador
12 | accessVector[recordID][heID] = false
13 End Function
14 Function retrieveRecord(recordID, userID):
15 | Checks if msg.sender is different from administrador
16 | if ownerVector[userID][recordID] == true accessVector[recordID][userID] == true
17 |   then return fileHashVector[recordID]
18 |   else return User does not have access to this Record.
19 End Function
```

Through the RecordControl smart contract, it is possible to perform some functions related to information storage. Initially, we implemented three vectors: ownerVector, accessVector, and fileHashVector. The first vector is manipulated when a Record is inserted, as it is part of the network that inserts it. It references the holder of clinical data, that is, the Patient. Therefore, all Patients are inserted in this vector and, for each one of them, their respective Records. The second vector refers to access control, and it is where all the Records that users have permission to access are inserted. In the fileHashVector, all the hashes of the files stored in the Off-chain Storage Layer are inserted. There are four variables used as function parameters: patientID, recordID and heID, which store references of the main database, and fileHash, the cryptographic hash of the stored media.

Note that there is a check at the beginning of all functions presented in the algorithm, as in line 2, which checks if the msg.sender is different from the system administrator. The variable msg.sender indicates who owns the implemented contract, that is, the address of the person who submitted the contract to the Ethereum network. Thus, this approach guarantees that only the Application Layer will perform the smart contract functions through the requests made by

the system. This strategy prevents calls from being made directly to the contract by means other than the Application Layer.

The first function of the smart contract is `includeOwner` which allows associating the Register index to the index of a given Patient in `ownerVector`, both are passed as a parameter. Such operation informs that the possession of the Record with `recordID` belongs to the Patient with the respective `patientID` attributing the value `true` to this position (line 3). In turn, the `fileHash` of the inserted content, which is also passed as a parameter in the function, is being stored in the position whose index references the added Record (line 4). Regarding the second function `includeAccess`, this one associates a Record to the participants who can access it. Thus, such functionality deals with the access control to each Record. In other words, the function receives as a parameter a `heID` and a `recordID`, indicating that a specific member of the network can have access to the given Register. For this, a value `true` (line 8). This function will be called when the Patient decides to authorize a health entity's access to clinical information that he/she owns.

The third function, called `removeAccess`, has the objective of disallowing the access of a health entity (`heID`) to a Record (`recordID`). Instead of removing, aiming at optimizing the contract to minimize costs so that it is not necessary to relocate all the positions of the vector, the value `false` is being assigned in the position of the `accessVector[recordID][heID]` (line 12). In turn, the fourth function `retrieveRecord`, retrieves the `fileHash` of the document referring to the Record stored in `fileHashVector[recordID]`. Therefore, it only returns the `fileHash` if the user who is requesting has possession or access authorized by the owner of the requested Record (lines 16 and 17). It should be noted that the function receives `userID` because both the Patient and the HE can call the function, but for the latter, the Record will only return if it has the proper permissions.

2. Off-chain Storage Layer

This approach proposes an off-chain storage layer of data related to the medical record to maintain the privacy of sensitive data and mitigate concerns about blockchain scalability limitations. The Record references information from Traditional Databases and for a Distributed Database. Initially, the Register inserted in the network through the `/insertRecord` request of the Application Layer is stored in the Main Database, represented by a table containing the attributes (columns). The Record has `heID` and `patientID` as keys (identifiers) that relate the Record to tables representing the health entity that inserted the Record and the patient holding the clinical information.

In turn, the media file of different formats generated or appended with the Record information is stored in a distributed database, specifically, Apache Cassandra. Apache Cassandra is one of the most popular NoSQL databases developed by Facebook. It is an entirely decentralized system and offers great performance, durability, and fault tolerance without compromising

availability. Cassandra has its query language called CQL (Cassandra Query Language) to interact with the system.

Among the different existing storage systems, we chose Cassandra because of its features and technical advantages mentioned above. Among the possibilities of storage systems, Cassandra was also chosen because it is not an immutable system like others. It provides compliance with the "Right of forgetting", for example, established by sensitive data protection laws. Such a right allows the data subject to exclude information that he/she requires within a system. However, this proposal aims to adapt to national and technical regulations and use such benefits.

In the Off-chain Storage Layer, the media file is converted to a hash using the SHA-256 algorithm. In turn, this hash will be stored in the On-chain Storage Layer. Since in the blockchain, the hash will be stored immutably, this technique will allow for future integrity checks of the original stored Record, serving as your fingerprint. In addition, a pointer is then formed that references the original file that is in the Off-chain Storage Layer to the On-chain Storage Layer, in addition to the identifiers coming from the Main Database.

3. Application Layer

This proposal highlights how this layer can communicate with others to access functionality related to blockchain storage consisting of an interface between the user and the On-chain and Off-chain Storage Layers. Thus, it is possible to make requests by the members and other functionalities to satisfy the SBIS requirements, such as using a digital signature. Participants such as the Patient, HP, ML, HI, can interact through the following requests:

- `/insertRecord`: Allows the participant to send a Registration to the network. Only the HP, ML, and HI can carry out the insertion of a Record since only these entities are legally responsible for issuing these documents.
- `/readRecord`: Allows the HP, HI, ML, and Patient to read a Network Log. In this case, this request returns the clinical data for viewing.
- `/authorizeAccess` ou `/deauthorizeAccess`: The Patient grants access for the HP, ML, or HI of the network to a specific Record. In this case, a third party will not be able to choose the record to be viewed. The Patient himself has the exam history list and will release the one that best suits the actual situation to the doctor. The Patient can also disallow the reading of a Record.
- `/digitalSign`: It allows the doctor to carry out his/her digital signature of the documents he/she produced and registered.

The Digital Signature Module is proposed to adapt the approach to some security requirements of the SBIS at a second level to allow that health information in electronic media can also be issued with the same degree of legality as the physical media documents (such as paper or film). In addition, the legality of these documents can be met in this approach as the SBIS follows the specifications of the Public Key Infrastructure (ICP-Brasil), a hierarchical chain of trust that enables the issuance of digital certificates for the virtual identification of the citizen in Brazil. The resolutions of ICP-Brasil specify the use of signature services to provide non-repudiation, identification and confidentiality, and the use of point certificates. ICP-Brazil is composed of a chain of Certification Authorities (ACs). The latter is a public or private entity responsible for issuing, distributing, and managing digital certificates. There is already a set of AC accredited to exercise such roles, as they meet the criteria established by the Management Committee of ICP-Brazil.

This module consists of a service that communicates with the technical development resources provided by ACs. Some private ACs have documentation that allows the integration with their APIs through a set of routines and patterns for their services without getting involved in details in the implementation of the AC's application. Thus, this module is adaptable according to the AC(s) chosen to integrate the approach. In this module, the media attachment is inserted into the Registry after digitally signing through the /digitalSign request.